

Full Length Article

Influence of zoledronic acid and pamidronate on tooth eruption in children with osteogenesis imperfecta

Natalia Del Rio Cantero^{a,*}, María Rosa Mourelle Martínez^a, Belén Sagastizabal Cardelús^b, Joaquín Manuel De Nova García^a

^a Department of Dental Clinical Specialities, School of Dentistry, Complutense University of Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain

^b Department of Paediatrics, Hospital Universitario de Getafe, 28905 Getafe, Madrid, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) is a congenital disease comprising a heterogeneous group of inherited connective tissue disorders. The main treatment in children is bisphosphonate therapy. Previous animal studies have shown that bisphosphonates delay tooth eruption. The aim of this study is to determine whether patients with OI treated with pamidronate and/or zoledronic acid have a delayed eruption age compared to a control group of healthy children.

Methods: An ambispective longitudinal cohort study evaluating the age of eruption of the first stage mixed dentition in a group of children with OI ($n = 37$) all treated with intravenous bisphosphonates compared with a group of healthy children ($n = 89$). Within the study group, the correlation (Pearson correlation test) between the type of medication administered (pamidronate and/or zoledronic acid) and the chronology of tooth eruption is established, as well as the relationship between the amount of cumulative dose received and tooth eruption.

Results: The age of eruption of the study group was significantly delayed compared to the age of eruption of the control group for molars and lateral incisors ($p < 0.05$). Patients who received higher cumulative doses had a delayed eruption age compared to those with lower cumulative doses ($p < 0.05$). There is a high positive correlation between age of delayed tooth eruption and Zoledronic acid administration.

Conclusion: Patients with OI have a delayed eruption of the 1st stage mixed dentition compared to a control group of healthy children. This delayed eruption is directly related to the cumulative dose of bisphosphonates and the administration of zoledronic acid.

1. Introduction

Osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) is a congenital disease that comprises a heterogeneous group of hereditary connective tissue disorders characterized by similar bone deformities and fragility [1]. The different clinical forms of OI include short stature, a blue sclera, dentinogenesis imperfecta, loss of hearing and scoliosis, among other features [2]. It is a rare disease of autosomal dominant hereditary origin, with an approximate prevalence of 1:20,000 live births [3].

Osteogenesis imperfecta traditionally has been classified in clinical terms. Silence established four main types of OI ranging from mild to lethal, based on the clinical and radiographic characteristics of the disease [4]. However, it is difficult to classify the type of OI based on the clinical appearance of the disease; as a result, in recent years there has been a tendency to classify OI according to its genetic mutations [5]. In most

cases there is a hereditary mutation in COL1A1 and COL1A2 [6].

In many cases, OI is characterized by craniofacial disorders and dental anomalies. Different studies indicate that only 22 % of all patients with OI have no dental alterations [7,8], with type I dentinogenesis imperfecta (DI) being the most characteristic manifestation. Approximately 30 % of all patients with type III and IV presentations exhibit ectopic eruption, and there is also a high prevalence of hypodontia and oligodontia in adolescents with OI [7–9]. Malocclusion is another frequent problem in OI, with skeletal class III malocclusion being a typical finding [9].

The therapeutic objectives in OI vary according to the phenotype and mobility status of the patient. Nitrogen-containing bisphosphonates (pamidronate, alendronate, risedronate and zoledronic acid) are currently the cornerstones of pharmacological treatment in pediatric patients with OI [10].

* Corresponding author at: Complutense University of Madrid, 28040 Madrid, Spain.

E-mail addresses: nrio@ucm.es (N. Del Rio Cantero), mrmourel@ucm.es (M.R. Mourelle Martínez), denova@odon.ucm.es (J.M. De Nova García).

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Bisphosphonates are stable pyrophosphate analogues with a long half-life when incorporated to bone and exert a number of effects, fundamentally including the inhibition of osteoclast activity [11]. Cyclic bisphosphonate infusion appears to improve the chronic pain in these patients, and bisphosphonate therapy (mainly disodium pamidronate and zoledronic acid) has become an established part of the management of moderate to severe OI [12,13]. Studies have been made of the effects of bisphosphonates upon growth, bone deformity, mobility and pain, with the observation of improvement in most cases. The duration of treatment once clinical improvement has been achieved requires a detailed study of each patient on an individualized basis [14,15]. Following administration, bisphosphonates are concentrated in the bone matrix where they can remain for months or years [16]. At present, OI is a disease that can be diagnosed from birth, and even in the intrauterine period. As a result, it is increasingly common for bisphosphonate treatment to be introduced from the first weeks of life. In addition, bisphosphonates are known to be efficient when administered in childhood, especially in patients under two years of age [17].

One of the problems observed in patients with OI is delayed dental eruption and the appearance of ectopic teeth. These alterations may be present as a result of the disease itself, or may be accentuated as a consequence of bisphosphonate treatment, secondary to alteration of the physiological mechanism of bone reabsorption around the dental follicle [18]. Tooth eruption is considered to be a valuable model for studying the bone remodeling process, since it involves closely coordinated processes of bone formation and reabsorption with the participation of osteoblasts and osteoclasts, respectively. The tooth eruption process is divided into two phases: intraosseous eruption and supraosseous eruption. During the intraosseous eruption phase the cells of the dental follicle play a critical role in recruiting and activating the osteoclasts around the crown of the tooth [19].

In order for the eruption process to occur correctly, the monocyte-macrophage cells (osteoclast precursors) must be recruited in the dental follicle during the pre-eruptive phase [20]. The osteoclasts form an eruptive pathway in the alveolar bone for displacement of the tooth [21]. We now know that the cytokine systems are implicated in the regulation of dental eruption, and research has focused particularly on the RANK / RANKL (RANK ligand) / OPG (osteoprotegerin) signaling pathway [20,21]. The RANKL/RANK/OPG axis regulates osteoclast maturation and bone resorption through activation of the transcription factor NF- κ B. However, the osteoblasts may influence the course of tooth eruption, also modulating the RANKL/RANK/OPG axis, since they synthesize osteoprotegerin, which is a bone reabsorption inhibitor, and RANKL, which acts as its inducer [22].

Dental eruption requires the reabsorption of alveolar bone, and studies in animals have shown that treatment with bisphosphonates delays the age of tooth eruption. In 1998, Grier conducted a study of dental eruption in rats that received injections of pamidronate, with the observation of delayed eruption of the incisors in the treated animals [23]. This phenomenon has also been seen in rats treated with zoledronic acid or alendronate [24–26]. Bradaschia-Correa et al. [24], likewise in animal studies, recorded the inhibition of molar root formation and eruption in growing rats that received alendronate – evidencing impaired activation of the osteoclasts, which remained in a latent state. In 2013, these same investigators published experimental data [25] showing that reduced expression of the receptor activator of NF- κ B (RANKL) inhibits osteoclast activation and dental eruption in rats treated with alendronate [24,27]. Subsequent studies by Hiraga et al. [26], involving the administration of zoledronic acid in rats, showed both tooth formation and eruption to be delayed versus untreated rats, and this delay moreover was found to be dose-dependent. When zoledronic acid was administered to older rats with already erupted incisors, no changes were observed in the timing of root formation, while the molars that had still not erupted showed a delay in both eruption and root formation. The evidence on similar effects in humans is limited, and few studies have shown a decrease in the number of clinically erupted

teeth in patients with OI subjected to bisphosphonate treatment versus healthy children [27], since most of them evaluated eruption age from radiographs [28,29].

If such effects are confirmed, the physiological process of tooth eruption could be affected (delayed), and the consequences would extend over the entire tooth development process, with different healthcare implications. The greatest consequences probably could be expected during the tooth replacement process (mixed dentition), with the need for closer patient control. Delayed eruption in these patients could require the extraction of primary teeth or gingival ullectomy in order to favor tooth eruption and thus avoid delays in orthodontic treatment.

The main objective of the present study was to analyze the eruptive chronology of the first phase mixed dentition (permanent incisors and first molars) in patients with OI treated with pamidronate and/or zoledronic acid versus a control group of healthy children.

2. Material and methods

A longitudinal, ambispective cohort study with a follow-up period of four years was carried out in the setting of the collaboration agreement between the *Fundación AHUCE* and the *Universidad Complutense de Madrid* (UCM)(Madrid, Spain) for development of the research project “Contribution of oral and craniofacial repercussions to the current diagnosis of osteogenesis imperfecta and its therapeutic modulation” (Supervisor: Dr. De Nova). The study was approved by the Research Ethics Committees of *Hospital Clínico de San Carlos* and *Hospital Universitario de Getafe* (Madrid, Spain), with supervision of its viability and the legal processing of healthcare information. The study abided with the Declaration of Helsinki and followed the guidelines of the STROBE statement. All the participants in the study signed the corresponding informed consent document.

2.1. Study group

The study group consisted of 37 children (19 males and 18 females) with an age of 4–9 years at the time of entry in the study. All of them were diagnosed with osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) and had received treatment with bisphosphonates. The patients were seen in the clinic of the Master in Pediatric Dentistry (Faculty of Dentistry of the UCM), and all of them met the following inclusion criteria: a confirmed diagnosis of OI and intravenous treatment with bisphosphonates (pamidronate and/or zoledronic acid). Patients with other associated systemic diseases were excluded, as were those with temporary dentition traumatism.

2.2. Control group

The control group consisted of 100 healthy children (52 males and 48 females). All of them were Spanish and Caucasian, with an age and gender distribution similar to that of the study group. These patients regularly reported for dental revision and were selected on a random basis and included in the study at the time of visualization of eruption of the first permanent tooth. The controls were required to be healthy and without temporary dentition traumatism. Those patients that failed to report for their revision visits every three months were excluded from the study. Following application of the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the final control group consisted of 89 healthy children (49 males and 40 females) with an age of 4–9 years at the time of entry in the study. We consider this number of subjects acceptable to be able to closely monitor each patient.

2.3. Data collection

2.3.1. Dental eruption data

The date of eruption of the teeth corresponding to the first phase mixed dentition was recorded in both groups. A tooth was considered to

have erupted when any portion of the crown had penetrated the mucosa and became visible in the mouth. Periodic revisions were made every three months during the period of eruption of the permanent incisors and first molars in both groups. Intraoral exploration was carried out using exploration material by one same operator. The chronological age of the patients was calculated from the date of birth to the date recorded as first visualization of eruption of each tooth. Data collection covered a period of four years. During the COVID-19 pandemic (2020) and population lock down period, the parents submitted the required information, sending us images of the clinical eruption of the corresponding tooth.

2.3.2. Pharmacological data

In the study group, and based on the clinical reports obtained during treatment, the data referred to the treatment cycles received were entered in table format, with inclusion of the following parameters: medication, cycle number, date of administration, dose, weight and cumulative dose. To estimate the cumulative dose, and due to the different bisphosphonate molecules involved, we used coefficients employed in previous studies (100 for pamidronate [PAM] and 10,000 for zoledronic acid [ZOLE], adjusted to 1 and 100 for PAM and ZOLE, respectively). The coefficients were based on the relative potencies of the molecules in inhibiting bone reabsorption in vitro [30]. These data were entered in a MS Excel spreadsheet that was also used to record the date of eruption of each tooth and the bisphosphonate dosage received up to that date.

2.3.3. Subgroups according to dosage

All the patients in the study group had received intravenous bisphosphonates at some point in life from birth until the start of eruption of the permanent dentition. The treatment was individualized for each patient, with modifications being made according to the observed clinical course. Two subgroups (low and high) were established according to the medication received at the time of eruption of each tooth (cumulative dosage). The first subgroup was characterized by low cumulative bisphosphonate doses with respect to the mean and median of the cumulative doses of the complete study group at the time of eruption of each tooth of the first phase mixed dentition, while the second subgroup was characterized by high cumulative doses with respect to the mean and median of the complete study group. The possible individual variations in treatment (different bisphosphonates and doses, together with a long eruptive process) implied that one same individual could shift from one subgroup to the other in the course of progression of the eruptive process.

2.4. Statistical analysis

After recording the time of eruption of each tooth, we were able to establish the chronology of eruption of the permanent dentition as well as the sequence of appearance of each tooth in the mouth. This was done both for each tooth individually and for each group of teeth, with calculation of the mean and median of the eruption ages in both groups. The Mann-Whitney U test was used to evaluate differences between the groups. The Pearson correlation coefficient in turn was used to evaluate correlations between the cumulative dose and the tooth eruption age, and between the type of bisphosphonate administered and the tooth eruption age.

Statistical significance was considered for $p < 0.05$. The SPSS version 28 statistical package for MS Windows (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used throughout.

3. Results

3.1. Chronology of eruption

The present study evaluated the eruption of a total of 360 teeth in the

OI study group and 635 teeth in the healthy control group. All of the studied permanent teeth presented a delayed clinical emergence age in the children with OI versus the control group. Based on nonparametric testing, the differences proved statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) on comparing the eruption age of the permanent first molars ($p < 0.001$), upper central incisors ($p = 0.016$) and lower lateral incisors ($p = 0.048$) (Table 1).

The mentioned delay was confirmed by the fact that at 9.52 years of age, all of the controls had completed eruption of the first phase mixed dentition, versus only 70.27 % of the children with OI.

3.2. Chronology of eruption and cumulative bisphosphonate dose

8 children received pamidronate alone before the onset of permanent dentition eruption. Of these 8 children, only 3 did not receive zoledronic acid at the time of eruption of the permanent molars. Regarding zoledronic acid, 3 children only received this medication at the time of the eruption of the permanent dentition, as did those who had received zoledronic acid only at the time of the eruption of the permanent molars. In total, 27 children had received pamidronate and zoledronic acid at the beginning of permanent dentition.

The cumulative bisphosphonate dose according to body weight was estimated by adding the doses received in each cycle, from the start until the date of eruption of each permanent tooth. On comparing the subgroups according to cumulative dose, the patients in the high dose subgroup were seen to present a statistically significant delay in eruption age with respect to the low dose subgroup for all the studied teeth ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2).

On applying the Pearson correlation coefficient, a strong positive correlation was observed between eruption age and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose in the case of the permanent upper first molars ($r = 0.663$ and $p < 0.001$) and the permanent lower first molars ($r = 0.772$ and $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 1). In the case of the central incisors, a marked positive correlation was observed ($r = 0.598$ and $p = 0.003$). Similar results were obtained on correlating eruption age and cumulative dose in the case of the lower central incisors ($r = 0.582$ and $p = 0.002$) (Fig. 2) and the upper lateral incisors ($r = 0.563$ and $p = 0.007$), with a strong correlation in the case of the lower lateral incisors ($r = 0.664$ and $p < 0.001$) (Fig. 3).

3.3. Chronology of eruption and its correlation to the type of bisphosphonate administered

Zoledronic acid was seen to influence the eruption age of the upper ($r = 0.532$ and $p < 0.001$) and lower central incisors ($r = 0.426$ and $p = 0.02$), the upper ($r = 0.561$ and $p < 0.001$) and lower lateral incisors ($r = 0.667$ and $p < 0.001$), and the permanent upper ($r = 0.512$ and $p = 0.007$) and lower first molars ($r = 0.688$ and $p < 0.001$). The correlations were markedly positive in all cases, with a delay in eruption age

Table 1
Comparison of mean and median eruption age (years) of the first phase mixed dentition of the maxilla and mandible in the study group versus the control group. *Significance level ≤ 0.05 .

Teeth		Study group		Control group		P-value
		Mean	Median	Mean	Median	
Central incisor	Maxilla	7.44 ± 1.02	7.26	7.25 ± 0.81	7.18	0.016*
	Mandible	6.8 ± 1.13	6.68	6.66 ± 0.88	6.61	0.78
Lateral incisor	Maxilla	8.65 ± 1.07	8.53	8.07 ± 0.75	8.2	0.56
	Mandible	7.76 ± 1.46	7.57	7.34 ± 0.85	7.33	0.048*
First molar		7.67 ± 1.4	7.31	6.92 ± 0.86	6.86	<0.001*

Table 2

Comparison of mean and median eruption age (years) of the first phase mixed dentition of the maxilla and mandible in the study subgroup with low cumulative bisphosphonate doses versus high cumulative bisphosphonate doses. *Significance level ≤ 0.05 .

Teeth	Dose subgroup	Eruption age					
		Maxilla			Mandible		
		Mean	Median	P-value	Mean	Median	P-value
Central incisor	Low	6.85 ± 0.96	6.99	0.032*	6.05 ± 0.76	5.81	<0.001*
	High	7.69 ± 1.15	7.37		7.28 ± 1.26	7.03	
Lateral incisor	Low	8.04 ± 0.71	7.89	0.002*	6.66 ± 0.82	6.78	<0.001*
	High	9.21 ± 1.14	8.95		8.51 ± 1.06	8.67	
First molar	Low	6.74 ± 0.89	6.58	<0.001*	6.46 ± 0.89	6.13	<0.001*
	High	8.51 ± 1.44	8.52		8.34 ± 1.52	8.45	

Fig. 1. Scatter plot showing the relationship between eruption age of the upper central incisors and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose relative potency (CD RP) (left) and of the lower central incisors and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose relative potency (CD RP) (right). AGE / CD RP.

Fig. 2. Scatter plot showing the relationship between eruption age of the upper central incisors and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose relative potency (CD PR) (left) and of the lower central incisors and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose relative potency (CD PR) (right). AGE / CD PR.

Fig. 3. Scatter plot showing the relationship between eruption age of the upper lateral incisors and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose relative potency (CD RP) (left) and of the lower lateral incisors and the cumulative bisphosphonate dose relative potency (CD RP) (right). AGE / CD RP.

being observed among the children that had received higher doses of this bisphosphonate. In contrast, pamidronate showed no correlation with the eruption age of the permanent teeth.

4. Discussion

The present study showed that children with osteogenesis imperfecta (OI) treated with intravenous bisphosphonates present a delay in eruption of the first phase mixed dentition compared with the healthy control group – with statistically significant differences in the case of the permanent first molars and lateral incisors. These findings support the hypothesis that bisphosphonate treatment slows the advance of the tooth within the bone crypt, and confirm the clinical impressions. Malmgren et al. [31] reported a delay in dental eruption in children with OI administered bisphosphonates versus children with OI that received no treatment, and healthy children. Furthermore, eruption was significantly delayed in the children that received zoledronic acid at some point versus the children that only received pamidronate.

Our study group is a sample of patients with OI, which is defined as a “rare disease” due to its low incidence. For this reason, the number of subjects is small, allowing the possibility of closely monitoring each one of them, and visualizing the eruption of each tooth at the moment it emerges in the oral cavity. Our sample of patients with OI is made up of 37 children, all with a confirmed diagnosis and who have received treatment with bisphosphonates at some point, being comparable with other similar studies, such as the Kamoun-Goldrat studies [27] where the sample of patients with OI was 33 children matched with healthy controls. In 2016 Vourimies [29] published a study whose purpose was to examine whether the timing of dental development in children with OI differed from normal and to obtain information on the effect of therapeutic doses of bisphosphonates on the timing of human dental development. In his research, he has a final study group of only 22 patients. On the other hand, Malmgren [31] in 2020 evaluated a larger sample, which consisted of 53 children and adolescents with OI treated with bisphosphonates and 121 children with OI who had not been treated with bisphosphonates. However, in this case, the age of the patients included in the study was broader, and it was a cross-sectional study with x-rays, where the direct collaboration of the patient was not required.

We have not taken into account the clinical classification of the patients with OI to classify them, because currently the treatment is individualized for each patient according to the clinical manifestations at the time of treatment, and for this reason this can be modified over time. Furthermore, sometimes we receive patients who have not been classified within a specific classification because the pathogenic mechanism of each subtype of OI is diverse, the clinical characteristics present a high heterogeneity.

The present study was based on a longitudinal design, which affords advantages with respect to cross-sectional studies, since the subjects were evaluated at regular time intervals, thus allowing more detailed assessment of the individual variations in each patient. In contrast to previous studies, we decided not to assess dental maturation using radiological methods, since panoramic radiographs in patients under 6 years of age would only be indicated in specific cases, and in our series most of the children were under that age at the time of entry to the study. Moreover, other authors conducting dental maturation and formation

studies in patients with OI using panoramic radiographs have reported as a limitation that in some cases imaging quality was not good enough to allow correct evaluation, and that structure overlapping occurred [28].

We considered a tooth to have erupted when any part of it was seen to emerge from the mucosa. Kamoun-Goldrat et al. [27] examined their subjects only by visual inspection of the four quadrants, and the number of delayed eruptions was determined from the classical criteria of Hurme [32], where a tooth was considered to show delay if it had not yet erupted within the specified age range. The mentioned authors compared healthy individuals versus patients presenting OI and administered treatment with bisphosphonates. The results evidenced a delay in eruption in the children with OI versus the healthy subjects. On the other hand, the study group was divided into patients that had received high cumulative bisphosphonate doses and individuals that had received low cumulative doses – with greater delays in eruption being observed among the subjects that had received the highest cumulative doses. At present, nitrogen-containing bisphosphonates (pamidronate and zoledronic acid) are the most widely used intravenous medication in children with OI. These two drugs have different potencies in vitro: pamidronate has a lower relative potency of 100, while zoledronic acid has a higher relative potency of 10,000. However, in this study, the type of bisphosphonate administered was not specified, and the relative potency of the drugs was not taken into account. In our series there were patients that had been administered pamidronate as well as zoledronic acid, in contrast to the study published by Malmgren et al. [31], where the subjects with OI received pamidronate as the only bisphosphonate. Although the administered zoledronic acid doses are lower than the pamidronate doses, and the frequency of administration is also lower, the fact that zoledronic acid has a higher relative potency in vitro suggests that it could be related to the observed delay in eruption of some teeth.

In our center few pediatric patients with OI have never received bisphosphonate treatment; we therefore were unable to establish a group of OI cases without such treatment. In 2017, Vourimies [29] compared patients with OI receiving bisphosphonates versus patients who received no such treatment, and found that the children that had not received bisphosphonate therapy presented earlier tooth eruption than the patients that had received such therapy. In this regard, the patients that had received bisphosphonate treatment would present a normal chronology of eruption, since the possible delay induced by bisphosphonate therapy would compensate the acceleration of eruption age induced by the background disease itself. However, the authors did not differentiate the patients according to the type of drug received, since the number of subjects included was small.

Dental eruption is mediated by bone remodeling and tooth development, which in turn depends on root development prior to the start of bone remodeling. Our study made no distinction between bone remodeling and root development, though there is scientific evidence suggesting that bisphosphonates only cause alterations at bone remodeling level. For this reason we chose to evaluate the first phase mixed dentition, combining the eruption process of teeth that require root reabsorption of the predecessor tooth (central and lateral incisors) and teeth that advance within the bone crypt without an erupted predecessor tooth (permanent first molars) in the course of a limited period of 3–5 years. Bisphosphonates have a very short half-life in the bloodstream (between 30 min and 2 h), though once absorbed by bone they can persist in the skeletal tissues for over 10 years – their release back into the circulation depending on the cellular turnover rate [33]. This highlights the importance of recording the cumulative doses received up until the time of dental eruption, since the amounts received are not the same in all patients.

In 2021, Taqui et al. [34] studied ageneses and retained teeth in patients presenting OI treated with bisphosphonates, and grouped according to the Sillence classification. An increased prevalence of over-retained teeth was recorded among the patients with type III and IV

OI, which presented more severe clinical forms of the disease and thus had started treatment on an early basis, before 6 years of age. In our study the patients were not divided into groups according to the clinical form of the disease, since treatment is currently individualized and all the patients had received therapy at some point before 6 years of age. However, the early diagnosis of delayed eruption may be a predictor of retention requiring some type of treatment to facilitate movement of the tooth towards the oral cavity.

In conclusion, we found that children with OI exhibit delayed eruption of the permanent first molars compared with a group of healthy controls. This delay in eruption is directly related to the cumulative dose of bisphosphonates and the administration of zoledronic acid. The data obtained should be taken into account considering the different conservative and orthodontic treatments which most of these patients need.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Natalia Del Rio Cantero: Writing – original draft, Investigation. **María Rosa Mourelle Martínez:** Supervision. **Belén Sagastizabal Cardelús:** Data curation. **Joaquín Manuel De Nova García:** Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the authorship and/or publication of this article.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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